

Participation of Teachers and Parents in the PAUD Parenting Program in Banjarmasin

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ABSTRACT

Parenting is A combining activities _ education received by children _ at school and at home . On activities This is coordination between teachers and parents students are very necessary . Study This explore How role as well as teachers and parents at the PAUD IT Assunah parenting program in Banjarmasin. Study done with use method qualitative . Primary data was obtained from interview in- depth and secondary data through document parenting activities at school . Then done data reduction and withdrawal conclusion . The result there is three stages parenting activities, namely , planning , implementation , and evaluation . Then parents _ has role active in parenting activities with fill in parenting activities through student parent association as resource person consumption and

INTRODUCTION

Family is the smallest unit in public Where every its members own the role of each, especially parents . Parents _ own role in operate function purposeful education _ For develop family as means education first and foremost as well as role as system internal controls for behavior child.

Iskaradah (2009), explains that parents also play a role in development children which includes : (1) nurturing health physical and mental child, (2) put base good personality, (3) guiding and motivating child For develop self, (4) give adequate facilities _ for development self child, and (5) create a safe , comfortable and conducive atmosphere for development child.

Mukhtar (2013) explains parental education _ is education provided _ to parents _ in frame For know and apply proper education _ in educate child age early especially moment child is at in environment family with his parents at home . One _ that way can done For increase knowledge and parenting skills _ in educate child can done with take part in a parenting program . Morisson (2012) states that parenting is something activity For help family so understand it development child , skills appropriate parenting, conditions _ supportive home _ learning child and help school obtain information about child . Yani, Khaeriyah , and Ulfah (2017) in his research mention parenting is wrong effort education carried out by the family with utilise available sources _ in family and environment _ _ activity Study in a way independent . parenting as an interaction process sustainable between parents and children _ those who cover activities give eating (nourishing), giving guiding , protecting children when they grow flower.

The concept of the parenting program is combine education obtained _ child at school with at home. Things should be become attention , especially For organizer education child age early . As institution education child age early should facilitate more Far For education parenthood or parenting. Activity Thisintended for parents capable operate his task as educator main for child and harmony with education received _ children at school .

There is hope parenting activities are help parents who have difficulty in apply pattern proper care _ to child , add outlook parent in knowledge parenting and psychology as well as health children and relationships communication between party school Good head school or teacher with parents of students . There needs to be cooperation between teachers and parents in education and also in organizing school activities in order to create good partners in the relationship between the school and the school community.

Suriansyah (2015) explained the importance of the family's role in the formation of children's cultural attitudes, so schools need to establish close cooperation with families, so that they can come together in one perception, attitude and action to try to prepare students to be ready to face future challenges through the schooling process .

In a society that is regulated by geselschalft mechanisms and norms , the family has a major and primary responsibility in its function to instill values, norms and the basics of socialization into subsequent educational institutions. The roles previously played by the family cannot now be carried out optimally

in accordance with the competency demands of global society. Therefore, this role is then played by the school with acting teachers as agent socialization

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

Approach used in study This is approach qualitative and use method narrative (narrative). Use approach qualitative with narrative method wants know and understand identity and views somebody with refers to the story educator / school principal in a way deep about planning , the process by which parenting activities are carried out happened , as well factor supports and factors inhibitor from the Parenting Program . Study implemented in May 2022 involves participant that is Principal of an Integrated Islamic PAUD school Assunah Banjarmasin. Data collection was carried out with interview deep as primary data and analysis related documents _ with parenting activities at school as secondary data.

After the data is collected researcher do reduce data to make it visible what is the process of parenting activities that have been carried out ? carried out , factors influencing inhibitors and supporters _ parenting activities . Then done data organization and retrieval conclusion to the data that has been presented .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Integrated Islamic PAUD Assunah is one _ leading PAUD school in Banjarmasin City on Jalan Bumi Mas Raya N0.12A, New Management, South Banjarmasin District, Banjarmasin City, South Kalimantan. Integrated Islamic PAUD Assunah founded in June 1991 founded by several _ individual who has vision , mission and goals the same education that is build based PAUD school character strong Islam . _ Total teachers and staff in Islamic PAUD Integrated Assunah there are 48 people.

Stages in Implementation Parenting Activities

Research results show there is three stages in implementation parenting activities in Integrated Islamic PAUD Assunah in involving parents _ students , that is planning , implementation , and evaluation .

1. Planning

Planning is something activity For prepare all something needed _ in implementation something activities to be carried out with Good in accordance with what was expected planning necessary parenting activities done namely :

- a. Parenting Program Socialization , namely school do socialization of parenting programs to all parents . _ Socialization can done when exposure about school programs when child register to school , parent meeting , via _ book liaison , letter write or circulars , leaflets , booklets, banners , brochures and through social media communication like Facebook, messages short (SMS), WhatsApp, Twitter.
- b. Formation administrator of the teacher parenting program , namely coordinator implementing parenting and cooperation

with parents of students called FSOG (Parent and Teacher Friendship Forum) from there you can covers distribution duties and placement of internal people formation arrangement committee consisting of activities from chairman , secretary , treasurer and responsible sections (committees). answer to fields technical requirements _ in support program administration . Example : sexy consumption , events section, public relationssection.

- c. Equalization perception is activity make program planning for clarification and parental understanding _ with PAUD institutions carried out through discussion with questions and answers , lectures , discussions For look for solution on various problems faced _ in activity meeting planning that.
- d. Identification need that is identification need information (issues important around education and growth flower child) who wants known by parents about long -term care This carried out at home . Identify need for parents _ concerning aspect material in education , care , pattern nurturing , health and nutrition , protection , stimulation education . From there it will be decided material what will _ discussed and appropriate sources _ with material to be lifted.
- e. Determine place and time , theme , facilities and infrastructure , media used , methods , target participants and attendance list.
- f. Drafting program plans and schedules activity that is compile program plan parenting if Already determine form activities and time to be held

2. Implementation

The implementation of parenting activities at PAUD IT Assunah is a form of collaboration between teachers and parents, where these activities are almost entirely filled by the parents' association (FSOG), both as resource persons, presenters, presenters, and one of the speakers

. The teacher's job is to coordinate the event and direct the parents according to the agenda and material to be discussed.

Management education in condition pandemic has push acceleration use various technology in the learning process , especially condition Study distance far , here become challenge for lots party not except for teachers and parents . On condition like This important for teachers to do communication with the parents of inner students develop various programs about progress Study child and also the problems that occur in learning child at home .

Forms of implementation of parenting activities that have been carried out carried out by PAUD IT Assunah that is online using zoom and also offline . Online parenting activities include the formation of a special IT team for the activity, thereby minimizing technical problems at the event. Meanwhile offline parenting is carried out in the Assunah multi-purpose building which is located in the Assunah school complex.

The implementation method used __ like ask answer . after giving material , parents _ welcome submit question to resource persons who have been prepared by the school and parents.

Source person in Parenting activities include lecturers , doctors , therapists and psychologists _ depends from material what you want We pick up at the moment that . The resource persons are usually early childhood education figures and parents of students themselves who have experience and scientific fields that are relevant to parenting discussions such as early childhood health, therapy for children who need special treatment but which parents can do at home, how to educate children. age early Good from attitude , kid nor abilities and skills child according to the characteristics of the child and so on. There are more parenting events at PAUD IT Assunah discuss about parents ' way educate child early age so that there is appropriate education between school and home or parents .

The results of Fitria's research (2018) show that not all PAUD institutions consider parenting programs to be important in PAUD institutions. It can be seen from the research results that there are still PAUD institutions that do not implement parenting programs. One reason is due to minimal knowledge about parenting programs. Apart from the lack of knowledge about parenting programs, PAUD institutions find it difficult to attract resource persons. Apart from that, PAUD institutions also find it difficult to invite parents because parenting participants (parents) are unable to attend because they work or have activities that have been planned, so Assunah Integrated Islamic PAUD should be an example in organizing parenting activities.

In the parenting activities carried out by PAUD IT Assunah, parent participation was very enthusiastic with proven the presence of parents at offline activities reached 300 people, parents active ask when the event takes place Because want to get input in terms of educating children at home.

3. Evaluation

Form of evaluation of PAUD IT Assunah parenting activities form meeting with the teacher regarding The obstacles faced by the event were the effectiveness of time, consumption, materials and the readiness of the parenting IT team so that happen repair on activities nextparenting a.

The supporting factor for the implementation of parenting activities at PAUD IT Assunah is the completeness of the school's facilities and infrastructure to facilitate the activities, including the building, IT team, sound system , LCD, food and most importantly, the readiness of the parents to collaborate with teachers in these parenting activities. . One of the attractions for parents to attend parenting activities is the door prizes provided by the Parenting committee, so that not only do they get knowledge about early childhood, parents also get mementos from the activities carried out.

In parenting activities, there are also obstacles that occur as in usual online activities form not enough the enthusiasm of the students' parents is due to activity taking place at the same time as other activities, for example while Work or while nurturing child, so level focus in understanding the material and enthusiasm ask reduced, meanwhile constraint offline usually in time management, _ activity A little delayedkar e na wait invitation namely the student's parents not yet present everything, but in anticipation of PAUD IT Assunah by means of if invitation has reach 50% event will started with welcome speech from school or FSOG, so When the main event took place, the invitees were already there attended 100%.

According to Yani, Khaeriyah, Ulfah in their journal stated "Islamic Parenting at RA At-Taqwa is an activity for parents/guardians of RA students which is facilitated by the school/RA to hold scientific presentations or studies on various themes related to early childhood education and care patterns (RA), with the aim of providing additional insight into theoretical knowledge and practical experience to parents/guardians in educating their children The Role of Teachers and Parents of Students in Parenting Activities In planning parenting activities it is important very considering the coordination of teachers and parents in its implementation, parents play an active role in parenting events such as being presenters, resource persons, prayer readers and other parenting activities in general done in family, however now parenting is not means the one who gave birth child. Parenting too can carried out in society among them through PAUD, parenting baby (baby daycare or use baby sitter services) or through mass media in order to create it positive parenting _ since early stage. At PAUD IT Assunah, parenting is carried out by all levels of education, including kindergartens, play groups and daycare. Engel et al. (1997) states Positive parenting since early in children will be very influential momentchild mature later even moment he get married and become parents. Caregiver positive tightly connection with ability something family / home ladder and community in matter give attention, time and support For fulfil need physical, mental and social of children who are in the growth period as well as for member family others (Nooraeni : 2017) the aim of holding parenting at PAUD IT Assunah is to provide parents with a proper understanding of how to educate early childhood, so that educational goals can be realized in real terms.

In planning parenting activities, when parents register their children at PAUD IT Assunah, they are given an understanding of the programs that have been prepared in the school activity calendar, one of which is parenting, parents are encouraged to come take part in activities and contribute in the form of collaboration or participation as a committee or participants in the activity. In line with this, in Ariyati's journal (2016), in implementing parenting, the steps that can be taken by play groups are:

- a. there is a joint commitment between managers and parents when registering their children in PAUD
- b. preparing a person responsible for parenting activities or management of PAUD
- c. identifying information needs (important issues regarding education and child development) that parents want to know
- d. preparing activity programs that will be carried out for parenting activities
- e. preparing activity schedules as well as determining sources or sponsors, for example, activities can be carried out once a week, once a month, or taking advantage of national holidays, depending on needs.

In planning and implementing it, teachers or schools have the responsibility to provide insight and understanding about the importance of this parenting activity. A number of traits and characteristics communication positive parenting according to PAUD Directorate (2020) is

- a. Clear
The message conveyed must simple , concise , as well easy understood
- b. Correct
Information provided _ No may be biased or gray in any sense
- c. Complete
Information must be conveyed in a way complete and complete
- d. Accurate.
The message conveyed must short and efficient time
- e. Reliability
What was said must Correct in accordance with knowledge he has
- f. Consideration recipient
- g. Politeness
Message must reflect low heart and decency to parents _ students(Prastika:2021).

By holding parenting activities every six months, it is hoped that parents can understand how to educate children and teachers can communicate and contribute to education at home by providing knowledge to parents.

Evaluation of parenting activities is carried out by the principal for the teachers, so that obstacles such as lack of effective activity time can be anticipated in subsequent parenting activities.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the discussion in the research sub-focus, it can be concluded that the process of implementing the parenting program at Raudhatul Athfal Permata Assholihin is: first, program preparation which begins with making a program plan made by the school principal and teachers. Planning includes place, date, time, location, resource person, theme, media, facilities and infrastructure as well as the form of parenting program, then forming the

composition of the committee (chairman, treasurer, secretary and sections), monthly parenting only from the school, yearly parenting involves committee or parents become treasurers, secretaries and committee sections in supporting the implementation of the parenting program; second, program implementation, starting with several preparations which include space, food, media, attendance list. Activities are held on Saturdays, starting at 08:00 ± 12:00 WIB and the parenting programs implemented are seminars, parent consultation days, field trips, regular meetings once a month (parenting), parenting in the WhatsApp group application held once a month. And third, program evaluation at Raudhatul Athfal Permata Assholihin is a discussion between the principal and teachers, then evaluation with parents is carried out through conversations between the principal, teachers and parents discussing resource persons and implementation materials. Conversations are carried out via cellphone or face to face.

The obstacles found in implementing the parenting program are in terms of time. There are still parents who are late or are unable to attend, even though the school has informed them before the implementation, either through circulars or via cellphone, namely the WhatsApp group.

Based on the research results, it can be suggested to school principals to invite parents to consult in preparing parenting program plans so that parents can know the program that will be implemented. Apart from that, parents can give suggestions or criticism. School principals should also invite parents to participate as resource persons so that cooperation can be established between the school and parents. Furthermore, in the evaluation process the school principal not only evaluates conversations between the principal, teachers and parents, but evaluation can be done in other ways, namely discussions between the school and parents.

Suggestions for schools namely there is development and renewal of parenting activities so that they are not monotonous in the method of implementation, while for parents it is hoped that parents will not come late and come according to the schedule that has been set so that the implementation of parenting activities runs smoothly and on time. Parents can occasionally become resource persons for parenting program activities so that parents can participate.

REFERENCES

- Adriana ,Zirmansyah(2018). Pengaruh Pengetahuan Parenting Terhadap Keterlibatan Orang Tua di Lembaga PAUD. Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, Fakultas Psikologi dan Pendidikan, Universitas AlAzhar Indonesia 1 (1), (28,3)
- Ariyati. (2016) Parenting Di Paud Sebagai Upaya Pendukung Tumbuh Kembang Anak Usia Dini. KHAZANAH PENDIDIKAN Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan, Vol. IX, No.2
- Arumsari,nurkamilah, adah. (2017) Pembinaan Parenting Bagi Orang tua siswa di PAUD dan TK Assaabiq Singaparna , Jurnal Abdimas Umtas-LPPM- Universitas Muhammadiyah Tasikmalaya, 1(1),(283)
- Febyaningsih, Nurfadilah. (2019) PELAKSANAAN PROGRAM PARENTING DI RAUDHATUL ATHFAL PERMATA ASSHOLIHIN, Program Studi Pendidikan Guru Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini, Fakultas Psikologi dan Pendidikan, Universitas Al-Azhar Indonesia, Jurnal AUDHI, Vol. 1, No. 2
- Fitria, (2018) Urgensi Program Parenting Di Lembaga Paud, Seminar Nasional dan Call for Paper “Membangun Sinergitas Keluarga dan Sekolah Menuju PAUD Berkualitas”
- Prastika. (2021) Parenting Modul 2 Peran Guru Dan Orang Tua Dalam Membangun Logika Anak, Banjarmasin: Haffecs
- Ismiati. Urgensi Program Parenting Bagi Orang tua Anak Usia Dini, Study Deskriptif Pada TK IT Permata Sunah Banda Aceh, Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh, (28,3)
- Lestari. (2019).Program Parenting untuk Menumbuhkan Kesadaran Pentingnya keterlibatan Orang Tua di PAUD.Pratama Widya : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini.4(1), (28,3)

Lestari, (2018). Psikologi Keluarga penanaman nilai dan penanganan konflik dalam keluarga, Jakarta: kencana preadamedia group

Nooraeni, (2017) Implementasi Program Parenting Dalam Menumbuhkan Perilaku Pengasuhan Positif Orang Tua Di PAUD Tulip Tarogong Kaler Garut. Jurnal Pendidikan Luar Sekolah,13 (2), (28,3)

Triamansyah, (2016) Manajemen Pendidikan Usia Dini, Bandung: Pusaka Setia